

Synthesis and Antimicrobial Screening of 1,2-Benzisoxazolyl Schiff Bases

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SCHIFF bases have gained importance because of the physiological and pharmacological activities associated with them. Schiff bases exhibit anticancer and antitubercular activity^{1,2}. Anticancer Schiff bases have been prepared by the condensation of aniline with substituted benzaldehydes³. Isoxazolyl Schiff bases have been synthesised as possible antibacterial and antifungal agents⁴.

In view of these important observations, some 1,2-benzisoxazolyl Schiff bases have been synthesised to study their antimicrobial activity. All the Schiff bases (I and II in Table 1) were prepared by the

condensation of 7-acetyl-6-hydroxy-3-methyl and 7-acetyl-6-hydroxy-3-ethyl-1,2-benzisoxazoles⁵ with several aromatic amines in presence of catalytic amount of piperidine in alcohol. The structures of these compounds were supported by elemental analyses and infrared spectroscopy.

Antimicrobial activity :

Some of the compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus*, *S. typhi* and *C. albicans*; but none of the compounds showed significant activity. The antitubercular screening of the compounds was carried out against *Micobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇Rv) by a Doub and Youmans' method⁶. Some of the compounds were found to be promising against *M. tuberculosis* (Table 1).

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA AND ANTITUBERCULAR ACTIVITY (in µg/ml) OF THE SCHIFF BASES (I AND II)

Sl. No.	Substituent R ²	m.p. °C	Yield %
<i>Compound I</i>			
1.	Phenyl	128 ^a	80
2.	2'-Methyl phenyl	155 ^a	82
3.	4'-Methyl phenyl	148 ^b	75
4.	3'-Methoxyphenyl	149 ^b	69
5.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	176 ^b	80
6.	3'-Chlorophenyl	142 ^b	85
7.	4'-Chlorophenyl	166-68 ^b	87
8.	4'-Bromophenyl	170 ^b	83
9.	3'-Hydroxyphenyl	215 ^b	68
10.	4'-Hydroxyphenyl	262 ^b	85
<i>Compound II</i>			
11.	Phenyl	94 ^b	68
12.	2'-Methyl phenyl	142-3 ^b	65
13.	4'-Methyl phenyl	95 ^c	70
14.	2'-Methoxyphenyl	99 ^c	72
15.	3'-Methoxyphenyl	100 ^c	68
16.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	95 ^c	75
17.	3'-Chlorophenyl	83 ^a	71
18.	4'-Chlorophenyl	149 ^b	75
19.	4'-Bromophenyl	166 ^a	72
20.	3'-Hydroxyphenyl	215-16 ^b	80
21.	4'-Hydroxyphenyl	203 ^b	82

All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

^a=crystallised from methanol,

^b=crystallised from ethanol,

^c=crystallised from 80% ethanol.

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Synthesis of 5-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-Oxadiazole-2-thione Mannich Bases and Their Biological Evaluations

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OXADIAZOLES have been associated with insecticidal^{1,2}, herbicidal³, antibacterial^{4,5}, hypoglycemic⁶, antitubercular⁷, antiviral⁸, antifungal⁹ and carcinostatic¹⁰ activities. Besides, 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione yielded Mannich bases with primary aromatic amines¹¹. It was therefore considered worthwhile to synthesise the title products incorporating the 1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione nucleus (Scheme 1) with a view to observe if such compounds could be of biological significance.

(Scheme 1)

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected.

5-(p-Methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione (I) :

It was synthesised by following the reported method of Young and Wood^{1,2} from p-methoxybenzoic acid hydrazide^{1,3}. The resulting crude product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 200°; yield 80%.

Anal : Found : C, 51.20; H, 4.0; N, 13.5; $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$ requires C, 51.44; H, 3.84; N, 13.46%.

IR ; (cm^{-1}), 1610 (C=N), 1180 (C=S)

3-Arylaminoethyl-5-(p-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (II) :

To a suspension^{1,4} of I (2.08 g, 0.01 mole) in 15 ml ethanol, were added 40% formalin (0.75 ml, 0.01 mole) and aniline (0.94 g; 0.01 mole). The reaction mixture was then warmed for 15 min on a water bath. It was then kept overnight. The product obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. Other such derivatives crystallised from alcohol and obtained in 70-90% yields are listed in Table 1.

The IR and NMR spectra of a typical compound 4 showed :

IR in KBr ; 3350 (NH), 1180 cm^{-1} (C=S)

NMR(CDCl_3) δ ; OCH_3 (Singlet) 3.78
 COOCH_3 (Singlet) 3.74
 CH_2 (Singlet) 5.4

Aromatic (Ar-H, Ar-NH-) multiplet 6.7-6.9 and 7.6-7.9.

Bio-Assay :

(A) Insecticidal activity :

The compounds in two concentrations^{1,5} (0.5% and 0.1% in acetone) were injected in the 3/4 abdominal segment of the adult cockroaches with the

TABLE 1—3-ARYLAMINOMETHYL-5-(p-METHOXYPHENYL)-1,3,4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONE (II)

Sl. No.	Amines	m.p. °C	Insecticidal activity	
			K.D. values (hrs) 0.5%	0.1%
1.	Piperidino	155	10	13.5
2.	Morpholino	166	12	14
3.	p-Carboxyanilino	258	9	13
4.	p-Carbomethoxyanilino	146	9.5	11
5.	p-Carbopropoxyanilino	150	10	13
6.	p-Carbobutoxyanilino	158	8.5	10.5
7.	o-Toluidino	180	10	14
8.	m-Toluidino	153-55	9	13.5
9.	p-Toluidino	148	10	13
10.	o-Carboxyanilino	231-32	9.5	14
11.	2,4-Dinitroanilino	174	8	12
12.	p-Anisidino	146	8	12.5
13.	m-Anisidino	136	9	13
14.	Anilino	136	10	15
15.	p-Chloroanilino	168	6	8.5
16.	p-Iodoanilino	191	10	12.5
	Acetone		36	
	Parathione		4	

The elemental analyses were found to be within satisfactory limits.

help of a microsyringe. The tests were repeated and the control was done with parathione. The K. D. values of other derivatives (II) are given in Table 1.

(B) Antibacterial activity :

The method, developed by Verma and Nobles^{1,6} was employed for the determination of the antibacterial spectrum of I and other compounds of Table 1. The test organisms included *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Sorsena lutea*. The bacterial cultures maintained at the Public Analytical Laboratory, U.P. Government were used.

Results and Discussion

The parent oxadiazole (I) inhibited the growth of bacilli significantly but this activity was decreased in the Mannich bases derived from it except those containing a nitro group which inhibited only *S. aureus* and *S. lutea* to the corresponding value of (I). The insecticidal activity was, however, enhanced in the Mannich bases (II) and most significantly when there was incorporation of a chloro group.

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Chemical Investigation of *Ochna squarrosa*

Linn

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OCHNA SQUARROSA Linn. (Ochnaceae) is a medicinally important plant used in Indian system of medicine for various diseases¹. The earlier workers reported the presence of β -sitosterol from the plant². In this communication we report three more known compounds-*n*-octacosanol, campesterol and β -sitosterol glycoside.

Experimental

Air dried powdered whole plant (2 kg) was successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and methanol. The petrol extract was concentrated and column chromatographed over silica gel. On elution with hexane-benzene 1:1 mixture resulted in a colourless material which on crystallisation using hexane yielded a compound, m.p. 84°. This compound was identified as octacosanol by comparison with an authentic sample.

The chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel and on elution with benzene afforded white solid, m.p. 156° which on acetylation with acetic anhydride-pyridine furnished the corresponding acetate, m.p. 138° identical with an authentic specimen of campesterol acetate.

Further elution of the column with chloroform afforded a glycoside, m.p. 284° which on hydrolysis with methanolic hydrochloric acid gave an aglycone m.p. 136-37°, identical with an authentic sample of β -sitosterol. The sugar moiety after usual work up was identified as glucose, by paper chromatography. Finally the glycoside itself was compared with an authentic sample (m.p. and m.m.p.) and was found to be identical.

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